

Helping Researchers Write Better Inclusion Plans

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The Astro2020 Decadal Survey report laid out an unprecedented number of recommendations for improving the workplace culture of the field. In response to these inclusion priorities, federal agencies, such as NASA and the Department of Energy (DOE), have signaled that topics around diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (DEIA) are important to the development of the workforce going forward. For instance, NASA has adopted inclusion as one of its five pillars of mission success, and several of its divisions require an Inclusion Plan as part of proposals. Similarly, the

DOE has introduced [Promoting Inclusive and Equitable Research \(PIER\) Plans](#) as an appendix to their proposal narrative that “will be evaluated as part of the merit review process and will be used to inform funding decisions.”

As part of the US Extremely Large Telescope Program (US-ELTP), the staff at NSF’s NOIRLab have developed a [Toolkit of Collaborative Practice](#) (Toolkit). The Toolkit originally was designed to be a product of the [US-ELTP Research Inclusion Initiative](#) and had been scheduled to be

Welcome to the US-ELTP Toolkit of Collaborative Practice!
The Toolkit has been designed to provide descriptions and best practices for a number of themes that support inclusive practice within scientific partnerships and collaborations. The Toolkit is organized as a curated database where the user can search for the subjects that are of interest in reviewing and/or adding to a proposal or inclusion plan.

Organization of the Toolkit:
Each row represents an activity, practice, or policy that can be added to an inclusion plan. Within each row, columns provide the following information:

Title
Description Information and definitions

Provide Feedback

Open Collaboration

Topic Theme Suggestions for...

Title	Description	Best Practices	Resources
Workload Equity Plan	Underrepresented researchers, including women scientists and scientists of color, may be disproportionately assigned tasks that are not considered as valuable as others within a research team. This unequal distribution of workload can lead to greater dissatisfaction and a higher likelihood of underrepresented team members leaving the team. To address this issue, it is important for collaborators to develop a plan for evenly distributing workload, including both valued tasks such as research and devalued tasks such as teaching and outreach. This will help create an inclusive environment where underrepresented groups, including women and scientists of color, are not disproportionately responsible for these tasks and have the same opportunities to engage in research as their colleagues.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a plan for how work will be distributed on the collaboration. This plan should clearly define roles and responsibilities; it is important that everyone knows what is expected of them early in the collaboration. Have a fair and transparent process for how tasks will be assigned amongst team members. Consider individual workload of each member on the collaboration. It is important to be mindful of other commitments individuals may have, their current workload, and their capacity to take on additional tasks. Have a plan for how tasks like mentoring or outreach will be assigned and assessed. Seek input from the team on how work should be allocated among them. Collect metrics that allow you to track whether the workload allocation process is working for the team. It is important to review and adjust as needed to ensure that tasks are being distributed equitably. 	null

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The Toolkit of Collaborative Practice is a filterable database that contains curated materials, including descriptions of DEIA themes and best practices. Researchers can use the information to tailor their own DEIA plans to the size and resources of their collaborations.

used to eventually support applications for broad community access to time on 30m telescopes. However, it is clear that there is a more immediate need for the Toolkit due to the new requirements for NASA and DOE proposal plans, which explicitly require principal investigators (PIs) to discuss DEIA.

The Toolkit is intended to provide principal investigators direct support in the designing and building of more effective activities that best suit their collaboration's size and readiness to engage in DEIA goals. In addition to providing links to web pages and articles, the Toolkit contains materials curated with the input and expertise of social scientists. It provides descriptions of themes that the PI may be interested in and provides a comprehensive list of good and better practices that proposers can adjust to their own needs and resources. Although many suggestions for good practice are provided, proposers are not expected to adopt every entry, but rather are encouraged to tailor their unique plan based on the best practice recommendations. Information on additional resources and citations are also available through the Toolkit portal and allow the PI to dive deeper into each theme as desired.

The Toolkit is set up as a filterable database that can be fully "opened," with all entries available, if the PI is interested in exploring all possible options, or that can be filtered to highlight specific recommendations, if the PI already has a theme in mind that they would like to know more about. This allows proposers to spend more time fully concentrating on

the planning of the activities that they are most interested in supporting.

The first version of the Toolkit includes 35 topical entries with themes that have been selected based on our report analyzing the review of Inclusion Plans written for the NASA Astrophysics Theory Program Research Opportunities in Space and Earth Sciences (ATP ROSES) [call](#) in 2021. The report identifies common (and less common) DEIA themes and provides an analysis of the grades that proposals received from diversity, equity, and inclusion expert panel members [1]. The Toolkit team used results from the report to select the initial themes that would be most useful to the community for version 1. We anticipate releasing version 2 in the summer of 2023, which will include additional themes and information about metrics for success, as well as enhanced guidance for panel members who want to use the Toolkit to better understand how best to grade proposals.

The release of the Toolkit enables staff to obtain feedback on Toolkit use and content from the community well in advance of when this resource is needed for investigators proposing for time on the US ELTs. The "Provide Feedback" link in the Toolkit offers a means for obtaining community input.

Reference

- [1] Sacco, T., & Norman, D. 2022, BAAS 54(1).
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